

Exploring the Spatial-Temporal Variability of Gas Consumption Within England and Wales: An Assessment of the Residential Sector Using Sequence Analysis.

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Summary

The UK housing stock is home to one of the most inefficient in Europe and has an overreliance of natural gas as a heating source. The consequence of this is a highly polluting sector which has not seen the relatively high fall in emissions that other large polluting sectors have. If the UK wants to meet its net zero target by 2050, its vital the sector de-carbonises. Spatial-temporal analysis will be used to track key consumption trends, such as areas of high consumption, areas where consumption is falling rapidly, or equally, areas which have always saw a low level of consumption. Observing these trends is vital for policy makers alike, as certain policies can be targeted towards individual areas to help the de-carbonisation process.

This study analyses gas consumption at the MSOA level from the year 2011-2019. Sequence and cluster analyses are applied to identify key spatial trajectories in decarbonisation. The characteristics of the clusters identified are contextualised with a range of spatial datasets representing the built environment, demographic and socio-economic factors.

KEYWORDS: Gas Consumption, De-Carbonising of the residential sector, Spatial-Temporal Variability, Policy.

Research Context

The UK's residential sector was responsible for over 70 million tonnes of carbon dioxide in 2019, which ranks it as the fourth most polluting sector behind transport, energy, and business. Since 1990 the residential sector has only seen a 15% drop in emissions (Smallldridge, 2020). What's responsible for this measly reduction is the continual overreliance of natural gas as a heating source in the majority of UK homes, combined with the UK having one of the most inefficient housing stocks in Europe (Smallldridge 2020; Broad, Hawker and Dodds, 2020). It's clear that if the UK is serious about its 2050 net zero targets, it has two routes. Firstly, the efficiency of dwellings needs to be enhanced, secondly the sector needs to ween itself from the reliance of natural gas and towards electrification generated by renewable sources.

A direct determinant of gas consumption is the efficiency of properties, which is tracked with an Energy Performance Certificate (EPC). These are assigned to properties each time they are sold/rented, which ranks efficiency from A (most efficient) to G (least efficient) (Maunder, 2019). Currently the Climate Change Committee stated all properties need to have an EPC rating of C or above within the next 10-15 years. Currently, the average EPC rating is 'Band D', with over 19 million dwellings having a rating of band D or below (Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, 2021). Those properties with lower EPC bands can require 3x more energy to warm, meaning members of these properties will be more likely to be living in fuel poverty (Department for Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy, 2021). The causes of fuel poverty are judged to be a multi-dimensional complex issue (Robinson et al., 2018), but there is agreement on several drivers, where inefficient dwellings are one of the most prominent (Thompson and Snell, 2013 and Boardman, 1991). As fuel poverty is directly linked to the efficiency of a property, it in turn massively influences the level of gas consumption of certain areas and is necessary to observe numbers and the spatiality of it.

The spatial context is imperative, as consumption and efficiency of properties is not be the same across the entire of the UK. Researchers have modelled the spatial energy intensity of the UK and discovered significant variation. Here, the South and South East were seen to have very low energy intensities, showing their homes are more efficient and require less energy to warm to a suitable level (Neto-Bradley et al., 2020). Furthermore, studies have shown clear correlations between consumption and affluence, a sense of an 'energy decadence' where the actions of certain individuals/households result in mass consumption of energy and are a strain on the energy system (Chatterton et al., 2016 and 2017). This makes the socio-economic characteristics of different areas highly applicable when looking at how consumption varies across the country.

However, the world we live in is not static, changes in energy efficiency of properties, socio-economic characteristics, and the types of heating fuel a property uses will change at different rates across different areas. For example, Morton tracked the socio-economic characteristics and location of individuals that were taking up energy improving retrofits under the Green Deal. Here, there were key geographic and socio-economic variations discovered in the uptake of energy saving technologies (Morton et al., 2018). This ensures that the spatial-temporal context is highly applicable with consumption, ensuring that high consumption areas that are not de-carbonising are potentially targeted for policy.

Research Questions:

- 1) *What is the spatial-temporal variation of gas consumption in gas consumption in England and Wales?*
- 2) *Is there spatial variation in areas that are leading the de-carbonisation within the residential sector?*
- 3) *How does gas consumption vary between socio-economic groups?*

Methodology: Data

Firstly, the Department for Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy have published the gas consumption for domestic properties for each Middle Super Output Area (MSOA) from the years 2011-2019 thanks to Xoserve. This enables observations on the changes in gas consumption in every MSOA over a long duration. There is a total of 7,202 MSOA's in England and Wales, where the mean population is just under 8,000. These MSOA's are small enough to potentially see significant levels of variation between them. This forms the basis of the sequence and clustering analysis.

In addition, a range of datasets will be used to contextualise the trajectories, The Office of National Statistics have produced outputs using domestic level EPC data published on Open Data Communities by the Department for Levelling Up, Housing and Communities. Here, over 12 million dwellings are used to produce a variety of energy performance data that has been scaled up to the MSOA level.

A variety of socio-economic data will be used at the MSOA level. Initially data from the 2011 Census will be effective, and later taken forward with the new 2021 Census (pending release this Spring). Data such as income, dwelling price, energy bills are all possible socio-economic variables that are possible to characterise the clusters.

These three datasets will later be linked together via their MSOA code. This will ensure that the spatial-temporal variation of gas consumption can be observed, and later analysis can be carried out to observe how consumption could potentially vary with socio-economic data overtime.

Methodology: Sequence and Cluster Analysis.

Sequence Analysis is a common type of analysis that identifies representative sequences of year to year transitions. Looking at spatiality, the aim of sequence analysis is to identify similar sequences of transitions between areas by measuring their similarity/dis-similarity to other areas (Pattias, Rowe and Arribas-Bel, 2021). Within the R programming language, the sequence analysis procedure is made easier by the TraMineR package (Gabardin et al, 2009), which will be used over the next coming weeks to develop the sequence analysis.

The gas consumption from 2011-2019 will undergo a sequence analysis which will enable each MSOA to have their gas consumption trajectories obtained. Leading on from this, a cluster analysis will be later ran on these sequences and later mapped. The hope is that each individual cluster will have a very different trajectory to other clusters e.g., clusters showing areas which have seen sharp falls in consumption and others which have seen a pretty stable trajectory.

Once the cluster analysis has been carried out, the characteristics of each cluster will be analysed using socio-economic and EPC data. For example, what are the socio-economic/EPC characteristics of each cluster that could possibly explain the trajectory of the cluster.

Results

To begin with, the results are the findings of initial data exploratory analysis within QGIS of gas consumption and EPC variables. Currently however, analysis is still ongoing.

From figure 1 below, which shows the percentage of dwellings that have the targeted EPC band of 'C' the CCC want every home to have within the next 10-15 years. It's clear that the residential sector is overall in a poor state when it comes to this EPC target. What's more is the large spatial variation however, where London seems to have large percentages of properties with EPC Bands of C or higher. This initial finding could be of significant policy importance, where there is a large difference across the county in the efficiencies of the housing stock (Neto-Bradley et al., 2020) and that low carbon technologies need to expand to areas with poorer EPC ratings.

Figure 1- Percentage of areas with an EPC band of 'C' or higher.
Source: Office of National Statistics

Figure two below expresses median gas consumption in 2019. What is first to note is the large spatial variation between the outskirts of the capital and the majority of the country. This links back to the 'energy decadence' finding of Chatterton and colleagues, where certain areas are responsible for large levels of consumption. However, towards the centre of London, consumption is low. This is likely due to a combination of efficient properties (figure 1) and the city centre housing lots of smaller properties/flats which would require less energy to warm relatively to other property types.

Figure 2- Median gas consumption in 2019

Source: Department of Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy

Figure three expresses the percentage change in gas consumption from 2011-2019 to explore if there was spatial variation in areas potentially leading the de-carbonising process. What is first to note is the positive overall fall in gas consumption across England and Wales, however there is spatial variation in the extent to which areas are seeing falls. For example, the South East has seen a smaller net fall in reduction when compared to other areas. This is once again important for policy and expresses the affluence and ‘energy decadence’ (Chatterton et al., 2016). As these areas consume more, targeting policy towards high mass consumption areas to install low carbon technologies would see the largest real term drop in emissions than other areas.

Percentage Change in Median Gas Consumption from 2011 - 2019 at MSOA Level

Figure 3- % change in median gas consumption from 2011-2019

Source: Department for Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy

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Biographies

Completed a BA Geography degree at the University of Liverpool. Later moved onto an integrated Masters/PhD at the Geographic Data Science Lab within Liverpool and E.ON acting as my project partner. Key research interests involve fuel poverty, spatial inequality and climate change.